

JOHN BLOWER'S PAPERS
Introduction according to archival international regulation¹
Pia Rigaldiès

Reference codes	From BLO/1 to BLO/7
Title	John Blower's Papers
Covering dates	1944-1980
Level of description	Collection, part of the EWCA's archives
Extent and medium of the unit of description	7 boxes and 77 linear cm
Language(s)	English
Name of creator(s)	John Blower
Brief biography	<p>John Blower was the first advisor of the Ethiopian Wildlife Organisation between 1965 and 1970. This new Ethiopian administration has been established after the Emperor Hailé Selassié requested assistance from UNESCO about wildlife issues.</p> <p>Graduated at the Edinburgh University, John Blower had several African wildlife experiences before joining Ethiopia in 1965: he has been game ranger in Tanganyika, in Kenya and chief game warden in Uganda.</p> <p>As advisor of the wildlife organisation in Ethiopia, he took part during five years in the creation of the first national parks in Ethiopia in 1969: the Awash, Semien and Omo parks.</p> <p>All the documents which are present in this collection are directly or indirectly the result of John Blower's activities in this administration.</p>
Archival history	<p>After the departure of John Blower in 1970, several other English experts took up the position of Wildlife Organisation's advisors: Melvin Bolton from 1970 to 1972, Patrick Stacey in 1972, John Stephenson from 1972 to 1975 and Jesse Hillman</p>

¹ Norme de description ISAD/G

at the beginning of the Derg period and until the 1980's. Jesse Hillman was very likely the one who made the first arrangement of John Blower's papers, putting it into folders and writing short overviews of the topics. These folders have been discovered at the beginning of the 2010's by Guillaume Blanc in the EWCA's library within the framework of his PhD research. John Blower's papers have survived the EWCA's move to Mexico compounds (Addis Ababa) in 2017.

Overview of content

- Wildlife conservation, regulation and establishment
- International Assistance and Missions
- EWCA's General Management
- National Parks Management
- Tourism, Safari and Hunting Issues
- Scientific Issues
- Miscellaneous

System of arrangement

The classification has been made according to the main issues of John Blower's missions and activities. The reference numbers given by the administration at the time were very helpful to create coherent files. Each file is arranged by chronological order.

Finding aid

The first column corresponds to the reference number of the boxes (from BLO/1 to BLO/7). The second part is the description of archival files related to the reference number. The third column corresponds to former reference numbers given by the administration (if written on documents). The last column contains the covering date of each archive's series.

Publications

BLANC Guillaume, *L'expert le dirigeant et l'habitant. La fabrique globale de la nature éthiopienne (1965-1970)*, « Génèses », Belin, n°115, 2019, pp. 53-74.

BLANC Guillaume, *Les territoires des parcs nationaux (Canada, Ethiopie, France) : logiques patrimoniales et nationales*, Université de Québec à Trois-Rivière, Université Paris 1 Panthéon Sorbonne, 2013.

HILLMAN, Jesse C. *Ethiopia: Compendium of Wildlife Conservation Information*, The Wildlife Conservation Society - International New

York Zoological Park - Ethiopian Wildlife Conservation Organization, 1993.

Archivist's note

The arrangement has been made by Pia Rigaldiès, last year student at the Ecole nationale des chartes (French national school for archivists) within the EWCA's archives project lead by Kidanemariam Ayalew and Guillaume Blanc.

Date of description

November 2019

**JOHN BLOWER'S PAPERS
Finding Aid**

BLO/1	● WILDLIFE CONSERVATION, REGULATION AND ESTABLISHMENT		1944-1975
	○ ● Wildlife regulation: also, draft regulation, correspondence		1963-1975
	○ ○ ● From 1944 to 1963		
	○ ○ ● From 1963 to 1972		
	○ ○ ● From 1973 to 1975		
	○ ○ ● Wildlife regulation from other African countries		
	○ ● National parks establishment		1969
	○ ● Wildlife conservation board	K/1 ; K/3	1965-1969
	○ ● Various general reports		1967-1973
BLO/1-2	● INTERNATIONAL ASSISTANCE AND MISSIONS		1965-1975
BLO/1	○ ● General: tables of foreign and international aids		1975
	○ ● Food and agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO) support	B/1	1965-1970
	○ ● Russian aids for development trough FAO	B/1	1965-1970
	○ ● Foreign Assistance		1965-1970
	○ ○ ● Peace Corps	F/5	
	○ ○ ● United Kingdom Assistance	F/6	
	○ ○ ● German government assistance	F/8	
	○ ○ ● United States National Parks mission	C/5	
BLO/2	○ ● UNESCO		1964-1971
	○ ○ ● Second UNESCO mission		
	○ ○ ● Man and the biosphere programme		

	○ ○ ● Other UNESCO reports and correspondence	B/5;B/6	
	○ ● Other		1968-1969
	○ ○ ● Ford Foundation		
BLO/2-3	● EWCA'S GENERAL MANAGEMENT		1964-1970
BLO/2	○ ● Budget	K/3	1964-1969
	○ ● Human Resources		1964-1973
	○ ○ ● Work's programme		
	○ ○ ● Job description (1) ²		
	○ ○ ● About John Blower's employment: correspondence with Tanzania National Parks		
	○ ○ ● Game Warden's Application		
	○ ○ ○ ● Employment of expatriate technical personnel, request for assistance	F/6	
	○ ○ ○ ● Game guards, general	J/7	
	○ ○ ○ ● Nominative files		
	Bromley (Eritrea)	J/5	
	Brown H. George (Omo)	J/3	
	Guth R. Laurence (Semien)	J/2;J/4	
	Hay W. Peter (Awash)	J/1	
	Nicol W. Clive (Semien)	J/2;J/4	
	Robertson (Awash)	J/10	
	Other gam warden's application	J/2	
BLO/3	○ ○ ● Request for job		
	○ ○ ● Other nominative files		
	○ ○ ○ ● Major Gizaw	Z/6	
	○ ○ ○ ● Ato Balcha	Z/6	
	○ ○ ● Staff member's journey with Ethiopian Airlines		

² Advisor for conservation education and publicity

BLO/3-	● NATIONAL PARKS MANAGEMENT	1963-1976
BLO/3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ● National Park's Equipment <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ○ ● General specification ○ ○ ● General equipment for camps and staff L/1 ○ ○ ● Firearms and ammunition L/2 ○ ○ ● Vehicles L/4 ○ ○ ● Aircraft L/6 ○ ○ ● Hotel concession L/8 	1965-1969
BLO/3	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ● Memoranda sent by J. Blower to various protected areas K/2 <p style="margin-left: 40px;">National Parks and others protected areas Human resources, staff Equipment Hunting, poaching, trophies Miscellaneous Memoranda received by John Blower (2)</p>	1965-1969
BLO/4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ● Awash National Park <p style="margin-left: 40px;">Boundaries and people transfer issues Accounting Monthly and annual reports Wildlife reports (records of games counts) Safari reports Visitors Human Resources, staff Radio Messages Equipment and constructions Jimma Hippo Pool Miscellaneous</p>	1966-1976
BLO/4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ● Semien National Park 	1963-1969
BLO/4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ● Omo National Park <p style="margin-left: 40px;">General Boat equipment</p>	1966-1969

BLO/5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ● Other protected areas and possibility for national park <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ○ ● Gambella <ul style="list-style-type: none"> General Lechwe Nile ○ ○ ● Danakil <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Field reports 1968-1969 Wildlife Human resources ○ ○ ● Harrar Province : report (1) ○ ○ ● Rift valley lake area : report (1) ○ ○ ● Gojjam : report (1) ○ ○ ● Blue Nile : report (1) ○ ○ ● Akobo area (1) ○ ○ ● Tendaho area ○ ○ ● Eritra ○ ○ ● Miscellaneous 	1965-1975
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J/6
H/5 ; H/8

BLO/5-6	● TOURISM, SAFARI AND HUNTING ISSUES	1966-1980
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BLO/5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ● Tourism and safari <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ○ ● General reports ○ ○ ● Safari organizations: correspondence ○ ○ ● Safari inquiries ○ ○ ● Safari reports ○ ○ ● Promoting German safari tourism: correspondence with Odo Willscher 	1966-1980
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BLO/5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ● Visitors <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prince Bernhard of the Netherlands Other visitors 	1966-1969
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BLO/6	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ● Hunting and poaching issues <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ○ ● Hunting regulations ○ ○ ● Hunting correspondence ○ ○ ● Animals capture, collect and translocation ○ ○ ● Birds issues ○ ○ ● Anti-Poaching team 	1963-1970
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I/1 ; I/3
D/1 ; D/2
E/5 ;
E/8 ;
E/9
E/10

BLO/7	● SCIENTIFIC ISSUES	1965-1971
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ● Zoological expeditions <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ○ ● Southampton University expedition ○ ○ ● Great Abbai expedition ○ ○ ● British Daalac expedition 	1966-1969 E/1 ; E/2 C/7
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ● Trainings for EWCA staff <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ○ ● College of African Wildlife Management, Tanzania ○ ○ ● Administration of National Parks, USA 	1966-1969 A/6 C/6
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ● Projects with museums <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ○ ● British museums ○ ○ ● Other museums 	1967-1968 I/8 K/10
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ● Scientific correspondence <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ○ ● Request for information ○ ○ ● Correspondence with international universities and research centers ○ ○ ● Correspondence with Addis Ababa University 	1965-1970 K/4
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ● Other <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ ○ ● Zoological Garden, Addis Abeba ○ ○ ● Visit to Dinder Park (Sudan) ○ ○ ● Communication (publication, television) 	1965-1971 E/3 H/6
BLO/7	● MISCELLANEOUS: ISOLATED DOCUMENTS	